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ESPAÑOLES, INDIOS, AFRICANOS Y GITANOS.
EL ALCANCE GLOBAL DEL FANDANGO EN MÚSICA, CANTO Y DANZA

SPANIARDS, INDIANS, AFRICANS AND GYPSIES:
THE GLOBAL REACH OF THE FANDANGO IN MUSIC, SONG, AND
DANCE

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CHANGING PLACES: TOWARD THE RECONSTRUCTION OF AN EIGHTEENTH CENTURY DANCED FANDANGO¹⁾

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Resumen:

El fandango, como baile de moda adoptado por la aristocracia del siglo XVIII y diseminado en salas de concierto y salones de la élite, tuvo sus orígenes en las fiestas de las clases más bajas de la sociedad española e hispanoamericana. Su amplia popularidad está ligada indisolublemente a las grandes tendencias sociales, económicas y culturales de la Ilustración, con su interés y ensalzamiento de lo popular. Sin embargo, aunque interpretados en ambientes aristocráticos y registrados en las partituras de los músicos de la corte, tratados de baile, *libretti* de ballet, óperas y tonadillas, así como en artículos de prensa y libros de viajes de aficionados intelectuales y turistas extranjeros, los fandangos populares se han perdido en el tiempo. ¿Es posible reconstruir un fandango bailado del siglo XVIII? ¿Qué revelan las fuentes principales acerca del vocabulario referido a sus movimientos, sus coreografías, y sus ritmos? Es más, ¿cómo podemos captar desde el punto de vista cinestésico la supuesta lascivia que, al igual que la representación de lo popular, caracteriza universalmente a este baile?

Palabras clave:

Juan de Esquivel Navarro, Juan Antonio Jaque, Pablo Minguet é Irol, Felipe Roxo de Flores, Antonio Cairón, pasada, cruce, llamada, carrerilla, campanela, bien parado, sostenido, cambio, pellizco, remate, fandango, seguidillas, sevillanas, folías

Cambiando Lugares: Hacia la Reconstrucción de un siglo XVIII de Danzas de Fandango.

¹⁾ Extracts (c.3000w) from “Almost Flamenco: Majismo, Urban Youth, and the Fandango Craze (1700-1849),” by K. Meira Goldberg from *Sonidos Negros: On the Blackness of Flamenco* by Goldberg, K. Meira (2018) are published here by permission of Oxford University Press, USA, www.oup.com. This material is view only and does not come under a Creative Commons license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/>), or any other open access license, that would allow reuse without requiring permission from OUP: For permissions, please contact academic.permissions@oup.com

Abstract:

The fandango, as a dance craze adopted by the aristocracy of 18th century Spain and propagated in elite concert halls and salons, derived from the communal celebrations of the lowest rungs of Spanish and Spanish-American society. Indeed, its widespread popularity is inextricably linked to the great social, economic, and cultural shifts of the Enlightenment, with its elevation and representation of the popular. Yet the popular fandangos, interpreted in aristocratic settings and recorded in the *cifras* of court musicians, dance treatises, libretti of ballets, operas, and *tonadillas*, as by elite observers and foreign tourists, have themselves been lost to time. Therefore, we wonder, is it possible to reconstruct a danced fandango from the 18th century? What can primary sources tell us about the movement vocabulary, the choreography, and the rhythms of the fandango? Beyond that, how can we kinesthetically grasp the supposed lasciviousness that, along with the fandango's representation of the popular, universally characterizes this dance?

Keywords:

Juan de Esquivel Navarro, Juan Antonio Jaque, Pablo Minguet é Irol, Felipe Roxo de Flores, Antonio Cairón, pasada, cruce, llamada, carrerilla, campanela, bien parado, sostenido, cambio, pellizco, remate, fandango, seguidillas, sevillanas, folías

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Five Women Composers for Guitar and Ernesto Nazareth: Brazilian Tangos (arranger), Mel Bay Publications.

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INTRODUCTION

The fandango as an eighteenth-century dance craze derived from communal celebrations of those inhabiting the lowest rungs in Hispanic society.²⁾ Introduced to the Iberian Peninsula by people returning from “the Kingdom of the Indies,” the fandango was perfumed by the boundless possibilities of the Americas, and soon became so popular and “so thoroughly naturalized” on the Peninsula that, as Henry Swinburne wrote in 1776, “every Spaniard may be said to be born with it in his head and in his heels.”³⁾ The fandango rose with the great tidal shifts of the Enlightenment, reflecting the emergence of new nation-states and new political and economic systems, in innovative performances for changing audiences. The fandango fascinates, because this once renegade and exotic dance came to represent the quintessence of national spirit in Spain. In a further ironic turn, this symbol of the metropolis was adopted as an emblem of local identity, voicing resistance to colonial culture in a glittering variety of locations throughout the Spanish- and Portuguese-speaking world.

There are references to parties of “black and white slaves” called “fandangueros” on the Iberian Peninsula as early as 1464, but although eminent theater and dance scholar Emilio Cotarelo y Mori (1911, ccxlv), and dance folklorist Aurelio Capmany (1931, 248) agreed that this dance must have been popular in Spain by the end of the seventeenth century, the fashion for the fandango among the upper crust is not documented until the early-eighteenth century.⁴⁾ Once adopted by the upper classes, however, the fandango’s trajectory becomes clear. Along with other popular dances such as seguidillas and jotas, and newer variants like the bolero, the fandango found a firm foothold on the Spanish stage in the second half of the century.⁵⁾ Along with these other dances, the fandango formed the basis for the escuela bolera (the bolero school, Spain’s school of classical

²⁾ We would like to thank friends, mentors, and colleagues Lynn Matluck Brooks, Alan Jones, Elisabeth Le Guin, Peter Manuel, Antoni Pizà, María José Ruiz Mayordomo and Aurèlia Pessarradona, Craig Russell, Paige Whitley-Bauguess, and Ana Yepes for their peerless research and seminal contributions to our work.

³⁾ Real Academia Española (henceforth RAE), 1732, 719; Henry Swinburne, 1779, 354. Unless otherwise noted, all translations are by K. Meira Goldberg.

⁴⁾ José Luis Navarro García, 1998, 59, 199, citing Municipal Archives of Jerez de la Frontera, September 14, 1464, folio 118.

⁵⁾ See Twiss, 1775, 167; and Lantier, 1836, 253.

dance), which in turn made the jump to middle-class dance academies and *café cantantes*, feeding into the vocabulary of present day flamenco dance.⁶⁾

Beyond impressionistic tourist accounts, the eighteenth-century fandangos of street and plaza were not recorded. And yet, looking to contemporary dance practices such as flamenco and classical Spanish dance, we wonder not whether they hold traces of the eighteenth-century fandango—as formal continuities in movement, music, and representational tropes are well documented—but exactly what these traces are. Therefore, we endeavor here to engage with the question of how to reconstruct a fandango from the eighteenth century.

Meira and Tom move toward the eighteenth century from opposite directions: Tom as an historic dance specialist steeped in the ethos of Renaissance and Baroque courtly styles, and Meira, as a flamenco dancer and historian, grounded in the world of the present and the popular. Jared, performer and scholar of both Baroque and flamenco guitar, straddles both worlds; as an accompanist moving fluently between music and dance, Jared helped us read and comprehend the musical sources. We seek here to explore and catalog the insights, intuitions, questions, and possibilities gleaned from our dialogue with the sources and with each other. We hope with our research to gather a body of possibilities to aid reconstructors in the future.

THE FANDANGO AS LASCIVIOUS

One question we were forced to confront immediately and continuously throughout our research is that of the fandango's supposed lasciviousness. Accounts of eighteenth-century fandangos danced in streets and plazas, on theater stages, and at aristocratic balls, beginning perhaps most notably with the often-cited 1712 letter by Manuel Martí y Zaragoza (1663–1737) comparing these dances to the “sweet tremblings” of the famously provocative *puellae gaditanae*, almost universally characterized this dance as licentious and lascivious.⁷⁾ Henry Swinburne, who attended a ball in Barcelona in 1775, wrote that the fandango “exceeds in wantonness all the dances I ever beheld. Such motions, such writhings of the body and positions of the limbs, as no modest eye can look upon without a blush!” (1787, 70). Contemporary tourist accounts of fandangos on the theater stage were also seen in this light; for example, William Dalrymple's 1774 account of *Travels Through Spain and Portugal* recounts how in several visits to the theater he saw the fandango, “a lascivious dance, brought from the West Indies” (1777, 51). Casanova, describing the fandango danced by couples at a masked ball in Madrid in 1767, said “I had never seen

⁶⁾ Cairón (1820, 110) says the bolero is an “imitation” of the fandango.

⁷⁾ Ortega Castejón, 2014, 306. We are grateful to Alan Jones for sharing this reference. For more on the *Puellae gaditanae*, see Kathy Milazzo, “Ancient Dancers of Cádiz,” in Goldberg, Bennahum, and Hayes, forthcoming 2015.

anything wilder or more interesting” (1966, 317). Casanova had seen the fandango danced in theaters in France and Italy, but those dancers “did not perform one of the national gestures which make the dance truly seductive” (1966, 321). He continued,

Each couple danced face to face, never taking more than three steps, striking the castanets, which are held in the fingers, and accompanying the music with attitudes than which nothing more lascivious could possibly be seen. Those of the man indicated love crowned with success, those of the woman consent, ravishment, the ecstasy of pleasure. It seemed to me that no woman could refuse anything to a man with whom she had danced the fandango (1966, 321).

Both Casanova and Swinburne voiced eighteenth-century tourists’ interest in seeing the fandango in its native, vernacular setting. Casanova noted that “to have a true idea of the dance one had to see it performed by gitanas (“gypsy girls”) with a man who also danced it to perfection” (1966, 317). Swinburne wrote, “The end of the carnival of Cadiz differed very little from the beginning; no public balls or masquerades being allowed ... There were however, many assemblies and balls of a lower class, where the fandango is danced a la ley, that is, in all the perfection it is capable of” (1787, 353–54).

For Martí y Zaragoza writing in 1712, part of the licentiousness of these dances involved their crossing class boundaries; they were danced not only by “dark-skinned folk and people of low station, but also by respectable ladies of noble birth.”⁸⁾ Half a century later, writer and critic Joseph Baretti, in a 1760 letter describing a fandango in Elvas, on the border between Portugal and Extremadura, noted that “shabby rascal[s]” danced with “gaudy women” without showing “the least partiality to age, to dress, or to beauty...”

This would not have been allowed in any of the countries I have visited, where the ill-dressed keep company with the ill-dressed, and the fine with the fine, without ever dreaming of such mixtures as are practised in this part of the world” (1770, 49–50).

This licentious intercourse between classes was a central trope of fandangos on the eighteenth-century theater stage as well, from Calderón de la Barca’s *Entremés del novio de la aldeana* (1723) to Mozart’s *The Marriage of Figaro* (1786). These fandangos were uproarious—their tumult, as Craig Russell argues in his article in this volume on Mozart’s fandango as a “prism of revolution,” having a decidedly political bent. It seemed to us that the class tensions shaping the fandango represented an opportunity to explore its embodied realness, to crack the carapace of its supposed lasciviousness and find out what movement,

⁸⁾ Alan Jones’s new translation of Martí’s 1712 letter from Latin to English is discussed in his article in this volume. An often-cited Spanish translation of this passage can be found in Capmany, 1931, 248.

what energy, what music, and what intentionalities lay beneath. How would the fandango have differed according to social context? Were we trying for a fandango of an aristocratic ballroom, of the theater, or of the street? Craig Russell, in his landmark study of the codex of Santiago de Murcia, personal guitarist and guitar tutor to Maria Luisa Gabriela of Savoy, consort of Felipe V and Queen of Spain, added another piece of the puzzle: dances on the stages of the eighteenth century were

...based upon the latest popular dances; the theatrical troupe merely transported the latest fad from street to stage ... Given the importance of dance in Spanish theater, one can assume that the variation-settings of bailes and danzas found in Murcia's "Código Saldívar" would be equally applicable to stage, street, plaza, or ballroom (1995, vol. 1, 17–18).

Tom and I decided not to decide, but rather to let the differences in our dance styles address this question.

Our Sources

We consulted a wide variety of primary sources in our research: dance treatises, sheet music, engravings and paintings, and tourist accounts.⁹⁾ The earliest mentions of the eighteenth-century fandango are those of the 1705 *Libro de diferentes cifras de guitarra*, which contains a "Fandango Yndiano" (Indiano means it comes from the Indies, that is, from the Americas) and a "Fandango" played with *rasgueado* (a strumming technique), and *punteado* (a plucking technique).¹⁰⁾

Calderón de la Barca's 1723 *Entremés del novio de la aldeana* gives stage directions indicating that the main characters stop "singing and playing instruments, and together they raise the ruckus, the shouting, and other things that are used when singing uproarious fandangos."¹¹⁾ This use of the word "fandango" to refer to both a raucous party and the dance and music presumably performed at those parties is constant, from the above-mentioned 1464 document castigating "black and white slaves" for raising a "scandal and a ruckus," to the present day; in his book on the Fandango of México, esteemed musicologist Antonio García de León Griego opens his chapter on "The Language of the Feet" with a

⁹⁾ For an overview of many of these resources, see Alan Jones, 2012.

¹⁰⁾ Craig Russell (1995, vol. 1, 157) gives the location of these documents: "Madrid: 'Libro de diferentes cifras,' BN, M.811, "Fandango," pp. 112–13; "Fandango Yndiano," p. 140."

¹¹⁾ "Deja de cantar y tocando arman los dos la gritería, chillidos y otras cosas que se usan cuando se cantan los fandangos en bulla," Pedro Calderon de la Barca, 1723, 90; cited in Cotarelo, 1911, vol. 1, ccxlv-ccxlv.

magical description of a nighttime fandango that can be heard from miles away (2006, 53).¹²⁾

In 1732, the Royal Academy defined “Fandango” for the first time, as a “Dance introduced by those who have been in the Kingdom of the Indies, done to the sound of a very happy and festive music.”¹³⁾ Also from 1732, Santiago de Murcia’s *Códice Saldívar* contains a fandango—one of the earliest notated settings of this music (Russell, 1995, vol. 1, 16). Around the same time, and in Madrid, engraver Pablo Minguet é Irol (c. 1715–1801) published a series of dance manuals—early Spanish dance scholar María José Ruiz Mayordomo (2012, 132) says perhaps beginning as early as 1725, and continuing through 1774—which give instructions for 45 Spanish dance steps “used in Seguidillas, Fandango, and Other Musics” (Figure 1).¹⁴⁾ This series of manuals was meant to instruct Minguet’s increasingly bourgeois readership on how to dance the French-influenced *contradanzas* of the day, but Minguet included this little treatise of Spanish steps, specifying that they may be used in French dances as well.¹⁵⁾

Many of Minguet’s eighteenth-century Spanish steps were already described in Juan de Esquivel Navarro’s 1642 *Discursos sobre el arte del dançado*.¹⁶⁾ This afforded us a sense of the continuities in movement vocabulary, as well as a perception of what had changed from the seventeenth to the eighteenth centuries. Another source, and a reference point in considering these continuities was dance maestro Juan Antonio Jaque’s *Libro de danzar de Don Baltasar de Rojas Pantojah*, a dance manual written c. 1680 for his pupil, which contains choreographies—lists of steps, lacking any spatial indications for the most part—for six dances.¹⁷⁾

¹²⁾ “...se quejan de los esclavos negros y blancos, (para hacer) fiestas se juntaban, é con panderos é tabales é otros estormentos—instrumentos—facían (escándalos) é bollicios...” Municipal Archives of Jerez de la Frontera, September 14, 1464, folio 118, cited in Juan de la Plata, “Esclavos, moriscos, y gitanos: la etapa hermética del flamenco” *Páginas*, n° 3, (Jerez, 1990): 76–84. We are grateful to Jesús Cosano for this reference.

¹³⁾ “Baile introducido por los que han estado en los reinos de las Indias, que se hace al son de un tañido muy alegre y festivo.” RAE 1732, 719, cited in Cotarelo, 1911, vol. I, ccxlv-ccxlv.

¹⁴⁾ We primarily used a 1737 version from the Library of Congress (henceforth LOC) and a 1764 version from the Biblioteca Nacional de España (henceforth BNE).

¹⁵⁾ LOC, 1764, 6. For more on the circum-Caribbean circulation of the *contradance*, see Peter Manuel, 2009.

¹⁶⁾ Our source for consulting Esquivel was Lynn Matluck Brooks, 2003.

¹⁷⁾ Our source for using Jaque was the transcription published by José Subirá in 1950. Jaque’s original manuscript can be accessed through the Biblioteca Digital Hispánica of the BNE, <http://bdh-rd.bne.es/viewer.vm?id=0000068465&page=1> (accessed July 23, 2015). For more on Esquivel and Jaque, see Ana Yepes, “From the Járaca to the Sarabande,” in Goldberg, Bennahum, and Hayes, forthcoming 2015.

Figure 1. Pablo Minguet é Irol, Breue tratado de los passos del danzar a la española [Texto impreso]: que oy se estilan en las seguidillas, fandango, y otros tañidos. Madrid: Imprenta del autor, 1764. Biblioteca Nacional de España.

Notwithstanding Minguet's descriptions of Spanish dance steps that can be used in the fandango, the floor patterns and choreographies that he provides are from French dance (he plagiarized liberally from French publisher and choreographer Raoul Auger Feuillet [1653 – 1709])—not the fandango (Russell, 1995, vol. 1, 23).¹⁸⁾ The first detailed description of a fandango choreography from a dance manual did not appear until 1820, when bolero dancer Antonio Cairón published his treatise on Spanish dance, disseminated throughout European dance academies in the works of Carlo Blasis (1828 and later).¹⁹⁾

¹⁸⁾ See Minguet, 1755, 6.

¹⁹⁾ For more on the fandango in Blasis, see Claudia Jeschke, "Hispanomania in Nineteenth Century Theory and Choreography," in Goldberg, Bennahum, and Hayes, forthcoming 2015.

SEEING THE PASADA

In his article in this volume, Alan Jones has re-worked the translation of Martí's oft-cited letter from the Latin original, and it turns out that it contains no reference to the fandango at all.²⁰⁾ What the letter does describe is a dance party in Cádiz, with couple dances in public plazas, much like the flamenco sevillanas danced in Seville during the April Fair today. Aside from sounding the theme of lasciviousness, commenting that the couples' "bodies move reflecting everything that awakens desire," Martí's letter gives much valuable movement description:

A man and a woman dance together, sometimes one couple, sometimes more. They move to the music, arousing lust in every way imaginable: by curving their arms in extremely soft gestures, moving their buttocks again and again, twitching their thighs, and provoking each other suggestively. They engage in all kinds of unbridled sexual mimicry with the greatest skill and fervor. You can see the man thrust his hips while the woman moans and writhes...

While they dance there is laughter and joking all around. What is more, the onlookers themselves, seized with the fury of the satyric dance, are drawn into this representation of desire, and they sway gently and nod their heads.

In terms of movement, we glean from this passage:

- A man and a woman dance together, sometimes one couple, sometimes more
- curving their arms in extremely soft gestures
- moving their buttocks again and again
- twitching their thighs²¹⁾
- provoking each other suggestively
- sexual mimicry
- the man thrust[s] his hips
- the woman moans and writhes
- While they dance there is laughter and joking all around
- the onlookers ...sway gently and nod their heads

²⁰⁾ The following discussion is based on Jones's translation of the Martí letter from Latin to English.

²¹⁾ Alan Jones makes the very significant observation that "the 'stamping' found in some translations appears in fact to be some kind of throbbing or twitching movement originating in the thighs."

Despite this detailed movement description, Martí's 1712 account gives no indication of the choreography, the patterns in space, of the dances he observed. However, the following eighteenth-century tourist accounts—and it should be noted that they are all from the second half of the eighteenth century, and all of “fandangos”—do give such indications:²²⁾

...men and women ... dance close to each other, then wheel about, then approach each other with fond eagerness, then quickly retire, then quickly approach again, the man looking the woman steadily in the face, while she keeps her head down, and fixes her eyes on the ground with as much modesty as she can put on (Joseph Baretto, 1760).²³⁾

...a young Spanish girl ... begins by extending her arms, making her fingers snap; which she keeps up throughout the whole fandango to mark the rhythm; the man turns about her, he comes and goes with violent movements, to which she responds with similar gestures... (Pierre Agustín Caron “Beaumarchais,” 1765).²⁴⁾

The fandango is danced only by two people, who never touch one another, not even with their hands; but to see them provoke one another, by turns retreating to a distance, and advancing closely again; to see how the woman, at the moment when her languor indicates a near defeat, revives all at once to escape her pursuer; how she is pursued, and in turn pursues him... (Jean-François Bourgoing, 1797).²⁵⁾

...the two dancers approach each other, they run away from each other, they chase each other in succession.... The lovers seem just at the point of falling into each other's arms; but, suddenly, the music ceases and the art of the dancer is to remain immobile... (Étienne François de Lantier, 1799).²⁶⁾

Today's sevillanas are the only couple dance in the flamenco repertory, and the *pasada*—the sevillanas step with which partners change places—is part of the sevillanas choreography in all its variants. But sevillanas are seguidillas; they are not fandangos. Why then would these eighteenth-century tourist accounts describe a *pasada* in fandangos?

²²⁾ The following sources are all included in Navarro García's appendix on the Fandango, 1998, 199–216.

²³⁾ Baretto, 1770, 48–50.

²⁴⁾ Thomas, 2006, 120–121.

²⁵⁾ Bourgoing, 1808, 300–301. See a discussion of this passage in Lou Charnon-Deutsch's article in this volume.

²⁶⁾ Lantier, 1836, 253.

FANDANGOS AND SEGUIDILLAS: SHARED DANCE SYNTAX

Perhaps partly due to their often-licentious reputation, Spanish dances have for centuries been notoriously fluid in name (Brooks, 2003, 34). And given the ambiguity of the word “fandango” itself, referring to both a dance music and to a party where a variety of popular dances might be performed, we should not be surprised to find this movement motif, like instrumentation, meter, and performance context, shared by these two old popular dances.²⁷⁾ Seguidillas can be traced to medieval Andalusian verse, while fandangos, somewhat younger, perhaps relate to the *décimas*, ten-line stanzas invented by Vicente Espínol (1550–1624). Both dances are endowed with a scandalous reputation: according to lexicographer and grammarian Gonzalo Correas (1626), seguidillas are elegant, sharp, and sententious, as befitting the dance of the *gente de la seguida*—the people of the pursuit—“ruffians and their consorts,” so-called “because they pursue their taste and their pleasure, a free, lawless life...and even because they are pursued by the authorities” (1903, 272).²⁸⁾

One formal characteristic that seems useful in differentiating fandangos and seguidillas is verse structure: fandangos have five lines, while seguidillas have three or four lines, often accompanied by a two- to three-line *estribillo* (chorus, tag). In sevillanas verses, the lines tend to alternate between 5 and 7 syllables:

Line 1:	Mi novio es cartujano (7)
Line 2:	pintor de losa (5)
Line 3:	que pinta palanganas (7)
Line 4:	color de rosa (5)
Estribillo line 1:	Así lo quiero (5)
Estribillo line 2:	Que pinte palanganas (7)
Estribillo line 3:	Color del cielo (5) ²⁹⁾

²⁷⁾ In their article in this volume, Ruiz Mayordomo and Pessarrodonna describe a fandango step that is very similar to the sevillanas step. Also in this volume, see Miguel Ángel Berlanga’s discussion of fandangos, jotas, and seguidillas as “fandango musics.”

²⁸⁾ ... dicho sentenzioso i agudo, de burla ó grave, aunque en este tiempo se han usado mas en lo burlesco i picante, como tan acomodadas á la tonada i cantar alegre de bailes i danzas, i del pandero, i de la jente de la seghida i enamorada, rufianes i sus consortes, de quienes en particular se les ha pegado el nombre á las seguidillas. I ellos se llaman de la seguida, i de la siga, de la vida seguida, i de la vida airada, porque siguen su gusto i plazer i vida libre sin lei, i su furia, i siguen i corren las casas públicas, i aun porque son seguidos y perseguidos de la Justizia...

²⁹⁾ For a performance of this verse, see Rocío Jurado singing in Carlos Saura’s 1992 film *Sevillanas*. Juan José Gallego Roldán, “Rocío Jurado – Sevillanas Corraleras,” YouTube, March 24, 2012,

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Il4hhkvdKWk> (accessed July 20, 2015), 1:11 – 1:51.

In her award-winning study of the *Tonadilla in Performance*, musicologist Elisabeth Le Guin cites philologist and folklorist Margarit Frenk in defining seguidillas precisely by this uneven verse structure, “combinations of “long” with short lines” that produce a ““limp” in the strophe” (2014, 109).

And yet, far from this sharp contrast in verse form (4-line “limping” verses in seguidillas, as opposed to 5-line octosyllabic verses in fandangos), in terms of dance, seguidillas/sevillanas and Huelva-type fandangos from Andalucía share an asymmetrical, limping rhythm:³⁰⁾

pam rest rest pam pam rest pam rest rest pam pam rest

in flamenco counts:

12 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11

If the verse above were being danced as a sevillanas, this would be the first *mudanza*, or movement phrase:

Mi novio es cartujano
pintor de losa

It would be sung something like this:

Mi novio es cartujano, mi alma,
pintor de losa
pintor de losa, mi novio es cartujano
Ay, ay, ay
Mi novio es cartujano, mi alma,
pintor de losa

The repeat of the first line would be danced something like this:

pam rest rest pam pam rest pam rest rest pam pam rest

in flamenco counts:

12 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11

Mi novio es Car tu ja no mi alma pin tor de lo sa pasada ————— change places
paseo (sevillanas step)

The sevillanas step that closes the line of poetry on flamenco counts “3–4” also begins the next dance phrase. That is, having changed places, the partners greet each other with the sevillanas step, which serves musically as a *remate*, or punctuation at the end of the line,

³⁰⁾ See Guillermo Castro 2013 for a discussion of adaptations of seguidilla meter to fandangos in both classical and flamenco contexts.

and also as the *llamada* (call), or opening for the new *mudanza*. (In flamenco terms, the *sevillanas* is danced in sixes, rather than in twelves, and thus the music simply resets back to the beginning of a new phrase following this *remate*.)

The *pasada* and the *sevillanas* step share a unique rhythmic impetus, launching forward on two consecutive beats (3–4, 9–10) instead of changing weight evenly. This asymmetrical rhythmic pattern is found in some of Spain's oldest dance steps, like the *paseo* or *sevillanas* step (Brooks, 1988, 201), and the *jota* step.³¹⁾ This danced *pellizco*, or pinch, pulls on the underlying triplet; in that sense, it functions as a *hemíola*.³²⁾

In dance terms this rhythm, which enunciates a change in section, step, phrase, or chord, serves the same syntactic function as marking alternate beats of the measure of 6/8 (12 – 2 – 4 etc. in flamenco counts)—some flamencos call this a *cambio*.³³⁾ The *pellizco* (on flamenco counts 4 or 10), which in both the asymmetrical *pasada* rhythm and the even *cambio* rhythm is accompanied by a movement upward and/or outward, as if tossing a ball in the air, leads into the *llamada* on a strongly accented first beat (12 or 6 in flamenco counts).³⁴⁾

The *llamada* may be followed by a pause lasting from two to five beats, a suspension replete with improvisational possibilities. Shared by all actors, this pause allows one participant or the other to take the lead, guiding the music toward resolution (as if catching and holding the falling ball) or, alternately, tossing it back up in the air, leading into another round of the improvisational game. This rhythm, a *hemíola* followed by a strong accent on the downbeat (a *cambio* followed by a *llamada* in flamenco terms), is a ubiquitous and essential element of flamenco syntax, found in *verdiales*, *fandangos de Málaga*, *fandangos del Albaicín*, *jaleos extremeños*, *bulerías*, and others. It is also present in Baroque music, as for example in Jean Baptiste Lully's "Vaya de Fiestas" from *Le*

³¹⁾ In his study of the *jota*, a popular dance in the northern provinces of Spain, Arabist Julián Ribera y Tarragó asserted that the Aragonese *jotas* derive from medieval Andalusian music, and returned there with the eighteenth-century *fandango* (1928, 66–67).

³²⁾ *Hemíola* is a rhythmic relationship, often an overlay, of threes and twos.

³³⁾ For a further discussion of this rhythmic pattern in *pasada* and *paseo*, and in *bulerías*, see Goldberg, 2014, 102–4.

³⁴⁾ See, for example, this snippet of Manuela Carpio dancing *bulerías* at the Festival de Jerez in 2012: in the first five seconds of this clip she pinches, throwing the gesture outward ("throwing the ball in the air"), on the 4 or 10 (in flamenco counts), followed by a *llamada* on 12 or 6 ("catching the falling ball") of each *compás* (measure) of six beats (roughly 00:08, 00:10), before "tossing the ball" back to the singer with a *pellizco* to begin a new line (roughly 00:12). FlamencoTV, "Manuel Carpio saca 'su esencia' en el Festival de Jerez, YouTube, March 6, 2012, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EZB87pcNVmw> (accessed July 20, 2015).

Bourgeois *Gentilhomme* (1670).³⁵ As we will explain in our discussion of *carrerilla* and *llamada* below, we think we may have found traces of this syntactic structure in Jaque's 1680 *Folias* as well.

In *sevillanas*, the *pasada* on the penultimate measure of the poetic phrase launches the dancers into the next *mudanza* on the closing six beats (*sevillanas* step).³⁶ It signals the coming end of the line of poetry even as it closes the dance phrase. Sung poetry and dance seem out of phase with each other, but, somewhat counterintuitively, the dancer grabbing ahold of the end of the phrase with this pinch may then control or guide it, extending the close to the limits of the participants' stamina, or bringing it to a witty or virtuosic conclusion. The *sevillanas* step ends on flamenco counts "3–4" with a *pellizco*, the lift in body and arms signaling that the "ending" will be the "beginning" of a new *mudanza*, on the following strongly accented first beat (12 or 6 in flamenco counts).

Today's *sevillanas* are quite academicized and, unlike most other flamenco dances, are usually taught and performed with a set choreography. But the eighteenth-century *fandango* would have been an improvised couple dance. This use of a *pellizco* or *hemiola* to close a phrase and open a new one in today's *sevillanas* illuminates complex syntactic relationships between dance, music, poetic structure, and meter, and hints at traces of improvised popular dance within the *sevillanas*' codified choreography. In fact, the motif of two pinched beats launching upward or outward as the dancer comments on or punctuates a verse is a fundamental element of improvisational syntax in flamenco dances

³⁵ In this recording of Lully's piece, see the phrase "de fantasia" from 00:50–00:56. Adriana Hernández Forcada, "Vaya de Fiestas, Jean Baptiste Lully, La Gallarda," YouTube, April 23, 2014, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eIppvf7eV6I> (accessed July 21, 2015). Meira presented part of her research on ties between Afro-Islamic-Andalusian verse structures and rhythmic motifs, and Baroque Spanish dance steps within *bulerías* in K. Meira Goldberg, "Celebration and Derision, Bulla and *Burlarías*: African and Gypsy Voices in *Bulerías*," paper presented at the annual meeting of the Congress on Research in Dance, Philadelphia, November 8–11, 2012.

³⁶ Fátima Elias, who learned *sevillanas* in her aunt's dance academy in her native town of Dos Hermanas near Seville, taught Meira this way of teaching *sevillanas* (thinking of the *sevillanas* step as beginning rather than ending the *tercio*). She also told her that she learned the *sevillanas* step as "*paseito*" and the *pasada* as "*cruce*"—this information was crucial to Meira's insight about the syntactic use of the *pasada* in *sevillanas* as applicable to the eighteenth-century *fandango*.

such as bulerías today, as is the placement of the cambio on the penultimate six, followed by a llamada which both closes and opens up the phrase on the final six of the verse.³⁷⁾

Might we apply this poetic-rhythmic syntactic structure of flamenco improvisation, present in the sevillanas pasada, to our eighteenth century fandango?

CHOOSING MUSIC: SANTIAGO DE MURCIA'S FANDANGO (1732)

We thought of Murcia's fandango because his is one of the earliest transcriptions, and because, although this piece may be intended for listening, it is based on dance music (BairdGoldbergNewman Example 1).³⁸⁾ It was particularly attractive in that, as Russell explains, it stands at the cusp of the Enlightenment's reinterpretation of the popular: "These new titles found in the 'Códice Saldívar No. 4' are among the first 'modern' settings of those musical genres to be found in Spanish culture: the fandango, jota and seguidillas" (1995, vol. 1, 16).

But Murcia's fandango is a sequence of guitar variations (called *diferencias* or *ritornellos* in the musical lexicon, similar to flamenco *falsetas*) that are variable in length and which, Jared explained, were meant to be repeated, extended, and improvisationally embroidered upon. Meira was concerned about the music's asymmetry, because sevillanas choreography is rigidly codified; each *mudanza* (*tercio* in flamenco terms, *estribo* in Cairón, 1820, 106) always has the same length. That is, to consider the choreography of a sevillanas verse as opening with an *entrada* (introduction) followed by three *mudanzas*, each beginning with a sevillanas step and finishing with a *pasada* (except the last in which the partners freeze in a *bien parado*, or held pose), each *mudanza* consists of a six-beat step repeated four times.³⁹⁾

³⁷⁾ This syntax can be seen in the Carpio video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EZB87pcNVmw>) at 00:45. Carpio does a llamada at the beginning of a sung estribillo, a two-line verse with two sixes in each line. On the penultimate six (00:47), she does a cambio, and a llamada (00:48) on what would be the first beat of the last six of the verse. But, in response to this llamada, the singer repeats the second line, shifting the phrase over by six, and re-synching such that what would have been the end is now the beginning. This sets in motion Carpio's exit, in which this operation is repeated, singer and dancer trading "tossing the ball in the air," leap-frogging over each other in beginnings/endings that fragment the sung phrases beyond intelligibility, converting them into a kind of rhythmic scating of voice and dance that builds to an intense close. See Goldberg 2014, 103–4 for more on this section in bulerías.

³⁸⁾ Murcia's Fandango (MS Folios 16–18) is reproduced in facsimile and transcribed in Russell, 1995, vol.2, 20–22, 138–42. We used the guitar transcription from Conservatorio de Música Juan R. Pérez Cruz, "Murcia, S. – Fandango – Transcripción para guitarra de Isabelle Villey," <http://bibliotecaperezacruz.blogspot.com/2014/11/murcia-s-fandango-transcripcion-para.html> (accessed July 23, 2015), included in the appendix of this volume.

³⁹⁾ In the verse sung by Rocio Jurado discussed above (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I14hhkvdKWk>), the *entrada* would be the declamation of the first line "Mi novio es cartujano, pintor de losa," 1:11 – 1:16, the first *mudanza* is 1:16 – 1:28, the second is 1:28 – 1:40, and the third *mudanza* is 1:40 – 1:51.

Murcia's Fandango is notated in 3/4, but Jared and Meira, thinking in flamenco terms, instinctively thought of this music in sixes. Some of Murcia's phrases fall into six "measures" of six, which could accommodate the length of sevillanas step + four six-beat steps + pasada. But not all of Murcia's variations were written in twelve measures. Russell comments on this as well:

Significantly, the phrases end suspended on the dominant harmony with no resolution to tonic. And cadences are conspicuously absent ... The resulting feeling [of the relentless triple meter] is one of melodic spinning and spinning; the chords seem to unravel, never quite tying themselves into a cadential close (1995, vol. 1, 52).

But then Tom made perceptive note of this passage in Cairón: "[the fandango's] duration is not precisely marked; and according to the caprice of whoever is dancing it may be longer or shorter" (1820, 100).⁴⁰⁾

In other words, the length for the fandango phrases in Cairón's time was flexible and depended on the dancer(s). This made us realize that, though the sevillanas are clearly relevant to our reconstruction, the eighteenth-century social dances from which they derive may have been more like flamenco today: flexible in length, and communicating transitions between sections through movement and music signals. Tom also noted that, while Cairón makes much of the *bien parado* in both the bolero and the *seguidillas manchegas* (from which sevillanas derive), in the fandango he does not describe these stops (although in 1799 Lantier, who saw fandangos on a theater stage, did). This made us listen differently to the Murcia, which has an introduction that could work for our *entrada* or *paseo*, asymmetrical variations that could work as *mudanzas*, with melodic signals (*caídas* or *cambios* in flamenco terms) at phrase endings, but no obvious stops. For example, we thought of measures 9–10 as the melodic signal that the phrase was concluding (*pasada*, or *cambio*), and measures 11–12 as the pause or suspension, reiterating the end of the phrase in order to begin a new one (*sevillanas* step or *llamada*) (BairdGoldbergNewman Example 1).⁴¹⁾

⁴⁰⁾ Please see a transcription and translation of Cairón's description of the fandango at the end of this article.

⁴¹⁾ Note in the Fandango Parao from Alosno in the province of Huelva, Spain, that the music contains exactly the same melodic structure as a signal to end the phrase and begin a new one. In this example, the melody begins at 0:07, at 0:12 the melody descends in tone (a *caída* in flamenco terms), and at 0:13 this melodic descent is reiterated as a signal for the dancing to begin, at 0:15. Rafael Fajardo González, "Fandango Parao en Alosno, día 24 de Junio de 2007, festividad de San Juan Bautista, patrón de la localidad," YouTube, September 26, 2007,

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=obKp9N6u8Pw&index=3&list=PLV8zAUL4Vic-Urmw09mao0lhyTwG_jPyr (accessed July 24, 2015).

We also thought the intensification of the music in the final variation (measures 61–77) was evocative of the last *mudanza* of the first *sevillanas*, in which partners perform a sequence of four *pasadas*, chasing each other dizzily before coming to a sudden stop. If we agreed to use the *pasada* as the movement analog to the musical cues signaling phrase endings, that would be a way for a couple to spontaneously respond to the unfolding, asymmetrical music. Perhaps using the *pasada* to signal the end of Murcia's phrases reveals traces of the *fandango* as an improvisational dance.

PASADA

The *fandango* choreography described in Cairón clearly echoes the choreography of *sevillanas* today. It has three sections, each opening with a *sevillanas* step, and each closing with the partners changing places.

The dancers standing one in front of the other...begin with the *paseo* (*sevillanas* step) ...

Right afterwards there will be a *mudanza*...and the dancers begin to pass, changing places (*pasar mudando el puesto*) ... The afore-mentioned *paseo* always follows (*se sigue siempre*) until having passed (*pasado*) and completed a revolution, finishing one in front of the other from which place they begin again with the *paseo*...as each did earlier in his previous place, to which they return with a *pasada* (*vuelven de nuevo a pasar*) to execute for the third time two more *paseos* with their respective *mudanzas*, with one of which the dance concludes (1820, 111–12).

Cairón's *pasada* (1820, 111) is clearly recognizable as the step we do today:

This *pasada* is done with certain open *pas de bourees* (*pasos de burea abiertos*), beating the sole of the foot on the ground (*batiendo la planta del pie en tierra*), bending the knees a little, and keeping the body very straight, and lifting or lowering the arms (see Figure 2).⁴²

Neither Esquivel (1642) nor Jaque (1680) lists a step called "pasada." But Minguet (1737) does: a "florete pasada."

The *Florete pasada* is composed of the same four movements as the *Florete natural*...but this is different from that one, only in that the step that has to come close to the other foot, doesn't come close, but rather advances, and for that reason it is called *pasada* (1764, 3).

⁴² We had originally read Cairón's word as "bariendo," and interpreted it as a typographical error for "barriendo" (brushing). We are grateful to María José Ruiz Mayordomo and Aurèlia Pessarrodona for the correct reading of this word as "batiendo."

In his description of Floreta natural (1764, 3), Minguet explains that this step, which recalls a pas de basque in the ballet vocabulary, consists of four movements: “bacío” (vacío), a lift of the leg, “rompido,” described by Esquivel “as one foot ‘cuts to the back’ the other one does the same action to the front, ‘as if one were ripping a paper with both hands” (Brooks, 2003, 113)—this step is like the flamenco chaflán—“passo” (step), and “arrimar” (to bring close). Minguet’s explanation is a direct quote from Esquivel (Brooks, 2003, 106–7, in Spanish, 220–21).

Spanish dance historian Lynn Matluck Brooks explains that the sevillanas step, or paseo, has been identified as “one of the most ancient and least altered” of Spanish dance movements (1988, 201). Cotarelo suggests that the pasada, or cruce (cross), is newer than the seventeenth-century paseo. Discussing the opaque allusions to popular dance in Esquivel, Cotarelo reveals the cruzado’s evolution from the seventeenth to the twentieth centuries:

All the effort of Esquivel is applied to explaining, in very obscure language, the basic and elementary movements ... It is evident that none of this ... is what we would need to know; as ... the cruzado that men and women do on stage would be an organic evolution composed between them; and what Esquivel defines is the simple movement of crossing the legs, as a common element of all kinds of dance.⁴³⁾

For Esquivel (1642), the *cruzado* was “the simple movement of crossing the legs,” while in Cotarelo’s day (1911) the *cruzado* was an “organic evolution” composed between a man and a woman on stage. It appears that the paseo or sevillanas step has remained much the same from Esquivel’s time until now, whereas the cruzado of Esquivel is very different from the cruce, or pasada, which Minguet described in 1737.⁴⁴⁾

⁴³⁾ “Todo el esfuerzo de Esquivel se contrae á exponer, en lenguaje muy obscura, los movimientos elementales y comunes á toda clase de danzas, como eran los pasos, floretas...vacíos...y rompidos. Como se ve nada de esto (útil para el que quiera aprender á danzar) es lo que necesitábamos nosotros saber; pues aun las palabras como cruzados, carrerillas y vueltas, que se hallan en las acotaciones de los bailes, solo en parte tienen el sentido que les da Esquivel. Por ejemplo, el cruzado que hacían hombres y mujeres sobre el tablado era una evolución orgánica y compuesta entre ellos; y el que define Esquivel es el movimientos simple de cruzar las piernas, como elemento común en toda clase de danzas.” Cotarelo, 1911, ccxxviii–ccxxix. This passage is taken from Goldberg, 2014, 97–98.

⁴⁴⁾ In their article in this volume, Ruiz Mayordomo and Pessaradonna point out, as Tom did, that the choreographic motif of changing places in both Italy and Spain dates to the Renaissance. Which begs the question—what changed to make the pasada the signifier of sexy Spanishness during the Enlightenment?

Figure 2. Marcos Telléz Villar, Un Pasar en las Seguidillas Bolerás. c. 1790, estampa aguafuerte y buril. Courtesy of the Biblioteca Nacional de España.

Minguet's floreta pasada is an open, or traveling floreta; the only difference being that the step that brings one foot close to the other in the floreta natural now advances. We found this to be significant in light of Cairón's ambiguous use of the word "paseo" to indicate both the beginning of the mudanza, as it is used in sevillanas, and the traveling step with which the dancers change places. Thus, Cairón describes how "this pasada" is done, and then says "el dicho paseo se sigue siempre;" it is ambiguous here whether the aforementioned paseo always follows or is always followed. That is, does "the afore-mentioned paseo" refer to the sevillanas step, which always follows the pasada, or to the pasada itself, which is the topic of the sentence? Cairón uses the term "pasada" completely unambiguously in his description of the bolero: "the man changing places with the woman, which are called pasadas" (1820, 106). The next clause in Cairón's fandango description, "hasta haber pasado y dado un giro, quedándose uno en frente de otro; desde cuya situación se rompe de nuevo con el paseo" (until having passed [pasado] and completed a revolution, finishing one in front of the other from which place they begin again with the paseo), might indicate that the same step, the paseo, is used to change places as to greet the partner on the other side. We thought that Cairón's ambiguous use of the term "paseo" might be consistent with the evolution implied in Minguet's floreta pasada, which seems to adapt an old step to a new choreographic intention. It is clear from eighteenth-century tourist accounts that the sensual pasada in which, while passing, both partners may lock gazes and even lean in toward one another, seeming "just at the point of falling into each other's arms" (Lantier, 1799), was a key distinguishing element of the fandango, and central to its seductive power.

CHOOSING CHOREOGRAPHY: JAQUE'S FOLÍAS (C. 1680)

Once we had settled on Murcia's music, and the pasada as a structuring device, Tom suggested we look at Juan Antonio Jaque's Folías as our choreographic template. Jaque's date, c. 1680, made sense. Also, Jaque references a vocabulary of steps that stretch from Esquivel (1642) through to Minguet (1737), and so we considered Jaque's vocabulary appropriate to our 1732 music.

Jaque's manual contains six dances, which contain no indication of rhythm or space, and little indication of whether they are meant to be danced in a ballroom or on a theater stage, by a soloist or by a couple. But Jaque's Folías interested us because it begins with an entrada and then repeats it after each of four mudanzas. We thought Jaque's entradas could correspond to our use of the pasada as a structuring device. In other words, we took each mudanza as a line of the verse, and took the entrada as our pasada + sevillanas step (freely interpreted, we admit). Tom explained that the Folías is notable in that the only other of Jaque's choreographies to repeat the entrada is the Villano (villagers' dance); we interpreted this as further support for our contention that the vernacular dances reflected in eighteenth-century salon and theater fandangos might have been couples dances structured by the pasada.

Some scholars see fandangos as related to folías (Hurtado Torres, 2009, 103). And Le Guin notes that in 1626 Correas used the terms “seghidillas” (seguidillas) and “folías” interchangeably.⁴⁵ Perhaps, given the illicit reputation of seguidillas, the seventeenth-century folías, a “frenetic” and “noisy” dance of crazies (which was nonetheless one of the “school dances” described by Esquivel) was, like seguidillas, a plausible antecedent for the fandango’s climactic sensuality and abandon (Brooks, 2003, 127, 138–39).

OUR PROCESS

Having made these decisions, we worked backwards. We identified six musical phrases in Murcia and began to choreograph Jaque’s mudanzas to each phrase. We used measures one through twelve (six sixes) as our entrada, mm 13–22 (five sixes) as the first mudanza, mm 23–34 (six sixes) as the second mudanza, mm 35–48 (seven sixes) as the third mudanza, mm 49–60 (seven sixes) to repeat the entrada, and mm 61–77 (eight and a half sixes) as the fourth mudanza. We fit Jaque’s mudanzas into the music keeping in mind the “pam rest rest pam pam rest” pattern of contemporary sevillanas and fandangos.

As an illustration of this process, the second phrase of Jaque’s Second Mudanza (1950, 195), is

... = floreta with the Right. Another with the Left, Salto backwards with the Right encaje with the Left. Reverencia cortada with the Right, Planta cuadrada and Vuelta de Pechos to one side Reverencia Cortada with the Left Planta cuadrada and Vuelta de Pechos to the other side =

We put this phrase, which we did on the left, into rhythm like this (Example 2):

The entrada in Jaque’s Folías ends with a step to the right, a step to the left, and a turn.⁴⁶ Meira noted that this step is similar to that at the end of a copla of sevillanas. Dancer Elisabet Torras Aguilera pointed out its similarity to the opening step for folk dances like jota and muñeira. Tom said it reminded him of the continenza, an Italian renaissance step meant to take in the continence of your partner. We decided to adopt this continenza as our “sevillanas step,” placing it on the last two measures of each of Jaque’s four mudanzas as a greeting of the partner before beginning the next phrase (it was already there at the end of his entrada, to be repeated after each mudanza). As the choreographic finish of the mudanza, and as a signal for this step, we inserted two floreta pasadas or a flamenco pasada on the penultimate six beats of each mudanza.

⁴⁵ Le Guin 109, cites Correas, 1626, 448.

⁴⁶ Paso a un lado con el derecho, otro a un lado con el Izquierdo, Buelta al Descuydo (1950, 195).

STEPS

The decision to work with Jaque's *Folias* meant limiting our movement vocabulary, and there are several movement ideas which piqued our interest but which will have to await further research. One is the *mudanza del amolador*, the knife grinder's move. Ana Yepes has been working on this *mudanza*, which is listed in Jaque's *Jácara* and in his *Paradetas*. The step is described in Bartolomé Ferriol y Boxeraus, a disciple of Pierre Rameau and author of a theoretical dance treatise published in 1745:

The amolador consists of making circles with the hand and index finger, at the same time that the foot on the same side lowers and lifts, while also imitating with the mouth the sound that the stone makes in this practice.⁴⁷⁾

We were intrigued by the suggestive insinuation of this action (grinding), and this character (a man who would have travelled unaccompanied from home to home and town to town). We wondered whether this allusive grinding action might have any relationship to that of the mill, a trope casting an attractive and provocative glow over the miller's wife or daughter, immortalized in many flamenco verses, as in Léonide Massine's *Three Cornered Hat* (1919), and in the folk dance from Galicia called the *muñeira* or *muiñera* (which means both "millstone" and "miller's wife").

We decided against castanets in our reconstruction, simply out of practical considerations for the acoustics of the space where we would be dancing, although we know from sources such as Minguet (1755, 7) and Casanova (1966, 321) that castanets would have been entirely appropriate. Despite the fact that Cairón (1820, 110) says *fandango* steps are "*rastreros*," or dragged (in contrast to the airborne steps of the *bolero*?) we also elected not to delve into *zapateado*, or footwork, which we thought would have required far more extensive research than that essayed here.

CARRERILLA

For many of Jaque's steps, such as *floreta*, we learned that Minguet had copied Esquivel almost word for word.⁴⁸⁾ This is true for the step *carrerilla*, "little runs," or "little gallops" (Brooks, 2003, 228: Spanish, 280: English). Meira had long been interested in this step, which appears in both the third and fourth *mudanzas* of Jaque's *Folias*, because a run forward with the body suspended over the balls of the feet is used as a *cambio* in flamenco. But as Brooks observes in her discussion of Esquivel's *carrerillas*, the Spanish version of a related step called the *seguito scorsò*, described in the treatises of Italian Renaissance

⁴⁷⁾ "El amolador es dar vueltas con la mano, y el dedo indice, al mismo tiempo, que el pie del propio lado baja, y sube, imitando tambien con la boca el sonido, que hace la piedra en este ejercicio." Ferriol y Boxeraus, 1745, 47 [p. 270 of the digitized document], cited and discussed in Yepes, in Goldberg, Bennahum, and Hayes, forthcoming 2015.

⁴⁸⁾ On *floreta*: Esquivel (Brooks, 2003): 220-21 (Spanish), 271-72 (English); Minguet (1764): 3. On *reverencia cortada*: Esquivel (Brooks, 2003): 227-28 (Spanish), 279 (English); Minguet (1764): 5.

dance masters Fabritio Caroso (1526–1600) and Cesare Negri (1535–1605), was done with one or the other leg leading; indeed, this alternation of the leading leg is implied in Esquivel’s description of carrerilla as “done with the left foot forward, or the opposite if they are reversed” (Brooks, 2003, 101-2).

Example 2. Jaque’s second mudanza to Santiago de Murcia’s fandango (measures 23–34).

In choreographing Lully's "Vaya de Fiestas," Yepes used this description to accentuate the music's hemiola placing a strong emphasis on the leading foot. In flamenco terms, the carrerilla became a cambio. In Jaque's Folías, carrerilla is always preceded by a llamada, a mirror image of the cambio into llamada pattern of flamenco, as of the pasada to end followed by the sevillanas step to begin the mudanza in sevillanas.⁴⁹⁾

Another fascinating aspect of carrerilla in relation to flamenco is Esquivel's use of the word "desmuñecando," in Brooks's translation, "working flexibly," to describe the action of the leading foot. Although we did not make this choice, this articulation of the ankle could easily have been interpreted as sounding the ball of the foot and the heel separately, not only in the light of today's flamenco vocabulary, but also considering eighteenth-century sources such as Joseph Baretti, who says that in seguidilla and "the Fandango especially," men and women dance quickly "striking...their heels and toes on the ground" (1770, 48–49).

LLAMADA

Minguet described the Llamada as "a natural movement...nothing more than...a step backwards, or to the side."⁵⁰⁾ But Brooks, noting how central this step is to the flamenco vocabulary, observes a discrepancy between Esquivel and Minguet's description of another step, floreo, in a llamada "done violently."⁵¹⁾ Minguet copied from Esquivel in describing "five movements of the Dance" as equivalent to those of fencing: "Accidental, Strange, Transversal, Violent, and Natural."⁵²⁾ Brooks explains that "Natural" refers to the "movement of the sword downward," while "Violent" refers to the movement of the sword upward—the term "violent" therefore applies to "steps that require upward aerial movement of the body, executed with considerable force" (2003, 95–97). Brooks interprets the llamada in Esquivel's floreo "as a simple, crisp stamp, based on the combination of 'violent' and 'natural' actions that Minguet calls for" (2003 106). We decided to follow her interpretation of the llamada in our reconstruction.

BIEN PARADO/ SUSTENIDO:

In contrast to his framing of the fandango as an old dance, Cairón calls the bolero "the most celebrated, the most charming, and the most difficult Spanish dance," and part of this qualification rests in the balance required by the bolero's sudden stops, its bien parados

⁴⁹⁾ Flamenco dancers will recognize the llamada followed by cambio rhythm in the classic llamada: 1 – 2 – 3 (4) – (5) – (6) – tico-tico-tico- pam-pam.

⁵⁰⁾ La Llamada es un movimiento natural, que no es mas que bolver un passo atrás, ò à un lado, conforme pide el tiempo que se ha de executar (1764, 8).

⁵¹⁾ Brooks, 2003, 106, 228: Spanish, 280: English; Minguet, 1764, 8.

⁵²⁾ "Los movimientos del Danzar son cinco, los mismos que los de las Armas, que son estos: Accidentales, Estraños, Transversales, Violentos, y Naturales" Minguet, 1737, 49.

(1820, 103). With grace and serenity, the dancer must suspend motion, revealing “with tranquility and pause the smallest gesticulations of the face” (1820, 104). Le Guin quotes dance folklorist and historian Juan Antonio de Iza Zamácola, “Don Preciso” (1756–1826) writing about this movement in 1799:

... at once, and as if spontaneously, the voice, the instrument and the castanets all stop, leaving the room in silence, with the dancers planted, unmoving, in various beautiful attitudes: which is what we call the Bien parado [Well stopped].⁵³⁾

Tom observes that, like the pasada, this artful freeze seems to echo a movement idea from the Italian Renaissance. In her article on style and performance in the social dances of Renaissance Italy, including considerations of improvisation, Barbara Sparti discussed “phantasmata,” meaning “ghost” (Italian) or “image” (Latin), deriving from the Greek word for “to appear.”⁵⁴⁾ The reference comes from Domenico da Piacenza’s c. 1455 *De arte saltandi et choreas ducendi*, who calls phantasmata “a body quickness’...that consisted in the dancer making a pause at every step, ‘as if—as the poet says—he had seen the Medusa’s head; that is, having made the movement he instantly and completely turns to stone’ ... standing still as death for a tempo (the equivalent of a modern bar of music).”⁵⁵⁾

Cairón begins his discussion of the Seguidillas manchegas by saying that it “is exactly the same thing as the bolero, since it consists in the same pasadas...and bien parados” (1820, 113). He seems to imply that the bien parado of the bolero comes from the seguidilla, but not from the fandango. And we have seen that, despite similarities in rhythm, vocabulary, and performance context, the verse structure of seguidillas and fandangos differs. Seguidillas verses are shorter—in the words of Correas (1626), “sententious.” Le Guin notes that in 1799 “B...n” observed that in seguidillas, the bien parado “was coordinated with the last syllable of the poetry” (as it is in flamenco today).⁵⁶⁾ In contrast, fandangos seem perhaps more discursive and, at least in Murcia’s music, one phrase tumbles into another without a clear pause.

⁵³⁾ “...y al señalar el noveno compás cesan á un tiempo, y como de improviso la voz, el instrumento y las castañuelas, quedando la sala en silencio, y los baylarines plantados sin movimientos, en varias actitudes hermosas: que es lo que llamamos Bien parado” (Zamácola, 1799, xii; Le Guin, 2014, 121).

⁵⁴⁾ Barbara Sparti, “Improvisation and Embellishment in Popular and Art Dances in Fifteenth- and Sixteenth- Century Italy,” in *Dance, Dancers, and Dance-Masters in Renaissance and Baroque Italy*, Gloria Giordano and Alessandro Pontremoli, eds. (Biblioteca di Danza, Massimiliano Piretti, Editore, Bologna, 2015), 142.

⁵⁵⁾ Barbara Sparti, 1993, 377, cites Domenico da Piacenza, *De arte saltandi et choreas ducendi*, Paris, Bibliothèque Nationale f. ital. 972, fol. 2r. See also Sparti, 1986.

⁵⁶⁾ Le Guin, 2014, 121–22 cites Zamácola, 1799, 9–10; and “B...n.” “Etwas über den Zustand der Musik in Spanien.” *Allgemeine musikalische Zeitung* 25 (20 March 1799) 391–4; 26 (27 March 1799): 401–5, and Beilage, xxxv–xxxviii.

We nonetheless doubted that the *bien parado* could have been a hard and fast distinction between *seguidillas* and *fandangos* of the eighteenth century. For example, flamenco scholar Faustino Núñez lists *El celoso chasqueado y transformación de Peliche el estudiante, tonadilla a tres* (The Jealous Lover Disappointed and the Transformation of Peliche the Student, a lyric comedy for three voices) of 1787 by Pablo Esteve; this *Fandango* includes a *bien parado* (2008, 314). Lantier's 1799 description of the *fandango*, "The lovers seem just at the point of falling into each other's arms; but, suddenly, the music ceases and the art of the dancer is to remain immobile," also clearly seems to describe a *bien parado*.

Both Esteve and Lantier's *bien parados* are danced on the theater stage. Musicologist Javier Suárez-Pájares explains that the *bien parado* was a theatrical innovation of the late-eighteenth century. He cites Juan Jacinto Rodríguez Calderón's satirical treatise on the *bolero* schools of Madrid in 1794 and 1795, listing the *bien parado* among the "new and scandalous steps introduced into the *bolero*," in which the arms "rise symmetrically until reaching the position of a thief when he is caught."⁵⁷ Suárez-Pájares quotes guitarist and composer Fernando Sor's 1835 encyclopedia entry on the *bolero*: by 1835 the *bolero*, which had been adopted by the elevated classes and had moved onto the theater stage, was "marred by poses revealing excessive abandon."⁵⁸ In fact, Suárez-Pájares explains, during the French occupation of Spain following Napoleon's invasion of 1808, the pressures on Spanish dancers to exoticize their performance in order to attract French audiences had already lead to the incorporation in the *bolero* of "gestures," "contortions," and "sudden movements" from "certain dances of the *gitanas*, the Gypsies of Spain," "whom the public would scarcely have suffered formerly."⁵⁹ It is clear in the eighteenth-century sources that these gestures, contortions, and sudden movements in the vernacular context were considered offensive because of their provocative sensuality. As Richard Twiss wrote in his account of *Travels Through Portugal and Spain in 1772 and 1773*,

There are two types of *fandangos*, though they are danced to the same tune: the one is the decent dance; the other is gallant, full of expression, and, as a late French author energetically expresses it, "est mêlée des certaines attitudes qui offrent un tableau "continue de jouissance" (is a scramble of certain attitudes that offer an

⁵⁷ "...que los brazos suban simétricamente hasta quedar en la figura con que pintan a un mal ladrón." Suárez-Pájares, 1993, 11-13, citing Rodríguez Calderón, 1807, 45-46.

⁵⁸ "L'origine de cette danse fut long-temps un obstacle à ce qu'on la reçût dans la bonne compagnie. Cependant, comme elle était noble, gracieuse, et que dans ses premières perfectionnemes on n'avait encore introduit aucune de ces attitudes qui marquent trop d'abandon..." Suárez-Pájares, 1993, 10, citing Sor, 1835, 92-93.

⁵⁹ "Des danseurs que le public n'aurait point souffert autrefois se présentèrent, et non-seulement ils ajoutèrent à cette danse tous les contorsions et les brusqueries dans les mouvements que Requejo avait proscrites, mais ils y introduisirent des gestes qui n'appartiennent qu'à certaines danses des *gitanas*, bohémiennes d'Espagne." Suárez-Pájares, 1993, 16-17, cites Sor, 1835, 96.

array of “continual enjoyment”) [Twiss’s punctuation] (1775, 156).

Likewise, in his 1760 account of a mixed-class fandango in Elvas, Joseph Baretti commented, “their gestures and attitudes are sometimes not so composed as one could wish” (1770, 48). Casanova’s 1767 account also seems relevant here: “Each couple danced face to face, never taking more than three steps...and accompanying the music with attitudes than which nothing more lascivious could possibly be seen (1966, 321). When we considered Cairón’s description of the proper attitude to strike in a bien parado (beautiful, graceful, serene), we started to wonder whether to read something akin to the bien parado, perhaps a folk antecedent to this theatrical innovation of the 1780s and 90s, in these descriptions of “attitudes” from the 1760s and 70s.

In his 1793 dance treatise, Felipe Roxo de Flores described a dance called “Paradetas...in which some brief stops in gesture and movement are done in consequence of the music playing, for which reason they were given the name Paradetas”—implying the dance’s name comes from the word “parada” or “parado,” meaning “stop.”⁶⁰) But this dance was not new in the late-eighteenth century; Jaque includes it in his 1680 manual and, interestingly, it is one of only two (the other being his Jácaras) to give indications of space and choreography; in this case, Jaque indicates that this dance is performed by a Lady and a Gentleman, before an audience.⁶¹)

We decided to think of our fandango not in terms of bien parados, or full stops, but rather in terms of *sustenidos*, suspensions. Recalling Lantier’s 1799 “falling into each other’s arms,” we found Brooks’s discussion of this step in Esquivel fascinating. Brooks explains that *sostenido* was mentioned by Esquivel as characteristic of the courtly *danza del hacha* (torch dance), and may have been used to heighten the suspense of that dance’s lively chases (2003, 142). She adds that the movement idea of suspensions used to heighten a dance’s dramatic effect was used not only in the Italian Renaissance *La Caccia d’Amore* (The Hunt of Love), but also in *folías*.⁶²) In other words, there is a precedent for using the *sostenido* to heighten the drama of a chase between lovers in this courtly dance of the

⁶⁰) “Paradetas, que es otro Bayle de la misma Escuela, en que se hace unas breves paradas en el gesto y movimiento a consecuencia del tañido de la Música, por lo que se le dió el nombre de Paradetas” (Roxo de Flores, 1793, 116).

⁶¹) Jaque, 1950, 197–98. For more on this piece, see Yepes in Goldberg, Bennahum, and Hayes, forthcoming 2015. In an email to Meira, Yepes says “the stops [in Jaque’s Paradetas] must be the quiebrós or caídas found throughout the choreography” (June 6, 2015). Yepes has reconstructed this piece, and has taught it at several workshops over the past year. For more information, see her website <http://www.donaire.eu/> (accessed July 27, 2015).

⁶²) Brooks 2003, 193, note 64, cites Negri’s description of *La Caccia d’Amore*, pp. 281–84; on *sustenidos* in *folías*: Brooks, telephone conversation with author, 10 October, 1994, and Lynn Matluck Brooks, *The Dances of the Processions of Seville in Spain’s Golden Age* (doctoral dissertation, Temple University, 1984 V44–45. For more on the love chases in the *danza de hacha*, see Esses, 1992, 664 – 67.

Renaissance.

Rather than articulating the sixth beat in a sequence of two *floreta pasadas*, we inserted a suspension, having changed places, which could accommodate a rotation of the bodies to face each other, and a long look between the partners before beginning the more formal *continenza*. We also danced the first *mudanza* completely on the first side (mm 13–16), then, after m 17, inserted a *pasada* (mm 18–19) and, having changed places, a three-count suspension (m 20), before the *continenza* (mm 21–22), which we found quite sexy.

CAMPANELAS

Both Esquivel and Minguet require the gesturing leg to be stretched in the *campanela*, which is “a hop on one leg while the gesture leg does a *rond de jambe*.”⁶³ But this involved too much elevation for Meira! And so, in light of how we knew this step would evolve in the flamenco vocabulary (toward a *cachucha* step, with the gesturing leg bent and raised higher), we decided to each do it in our own style.⁶⁴ In our research on the *campanela*, we came across Marcos Telléz Villar’s image (see Figure 3).

We adopted this image’s arms and slight lean away from the gesturing leg for our *campanelas*, and played with them in our *pasadas* as well. The lean seemed to clue us into a movement idea that, like the *pasada* and the *bien parado*, would come to signify the sensuality and exoticism of Spanish dance by the nineteenth century. Thus, in 1642, Esquivel equated a dancer’s deviation from corporeal as from moral rectitude: “with the effrontery that is here worked, it is permitted to tilt, lean, and let the body sag.”⁶⁵ In contrast, by 1845, Romantic dance critic Théophile Gautier saw in the leans and bends of renowned ballerina Fanny Elssler’s *Cachucha* the quintessence of Spanish sensuality: “Her wasp-like figure is boldly arched back...How she twists! How she bends! ... Her swooning arms flutter about her drooping head, her body curves back, her white shoulders almost brush the floor” (Gautier, 1845, 15).

⁶³ “The Spanish version of the *campanela* is a hop on one leg while the gesture leg does a *rond de jambe* tracing the circumference of the bell from the front around equally to the back, the gesture foot passing the toes of the hopping foot twice, once at the start and once at the end of the action...must be done with control, landing softly, keeping the ‘bell’ low, level, even from front to back, and the leg stretched” (Brooks 2003 100). “La Campanela sola de por si, y no acompañada, no es mas que un movimiento simple, y se hace bien redonda, de esta forma: saltando sobre un pie, y obrandola con el otro, de modo, que al acabar el salto, y executar la campanela, sea todo uno, y ha de salir el pie al comenzarlo por la punta del otro pie dos veces, haciendo un circulo redondo, cogiendo tanto circuito, y compàs de atrás, como de adelante, llevando la punta del pie bien derecha, sin encoger la pierna, y executandola con mucha suavidad: llamase campanela, porque mientras mas redonda es mejor, y por un nivèl, como un cerco de una campana” (Minguet 1764 7).

⁶⁴ For more on this step in the nineteenth century, see Goldberg, 2014, 94–96.

⁶⁵ “Con el desgarró que se obra, consiente el ladear, cargar, y bajar el cuerpo.” Brooks, 1988, 199; Brooks gives a slightly different translation of Esquivel’s phrase in *The Art of Dancing in Seventeenth-Century Spain*, 2003, 280 (Spanish on p. 228).

CONCLUSION: PASADA SIGNIFIES LASCIVIOUSNESS AND INTERCOURSE BETWEEN CLASSES

Should the entrada be a minuet-like greeting to the king or a sevillanas-like circling of the partner? How balletic, how folksy should the movement style be? How heavy? How light? How straight the leg? How big the arms? How many hips? How much bend at the waist? Tracing genealogical relationships between embodied ideas is always a delicate, subjective, and conditional matter. Within the shifting winds driving the fandango's cross-class and cross-cultural pollination, we decided to frame these questions as decisions to research and to articulate.

Proposing the pasada as a way for a couple to have improvisationally responded to music, we seek in Murcia's fandango traces of its vernacular roots. In the pasada, the rhythmic pinch marking two consecutive beats adds impetus and passion to the flirtatious exchange. The pasada speaks of desire, and its syntactic use speaks of agency as well—disrupting a stable walking rhythm, a dancer thrusts his or her weight into the musical stream, shaping its flow. (In flamenco terms, this is to *pellizar el cante*.) Like the *sostenido/ bien parado*, we see in the pasada not only the eighteenth century's elevation of the popular, but also the revolutionary spirit of this era, the Enlightenment's yearning for cross-class mobility, for the freedom to invent one's self. Seen in this light, the fandango's expression of desire is an early manifestation of the development of modern subjectivity, elaborated in the act of recognizing, and changing places with, the Other.

CAIRÓN ON FANDANGO (1820, 100–13)

Baile antiguo español, y el que se ha conservado mas tiempo : el fandango, como la mayor parte de los bailes españoles, es de un tiempo ternario, alegre y vivo : no tiene marcada precisamente su duración; y según el capricho de quien lo baila, puede ser mas larga ó corta. El fandango tiene mucha gracia: no es un baile de tanta capacidad como el bolero, ni se requiere tanto arte para bailarlo, pues aunque el bolero sea en parte una imitación del fandango, con todo, este último es mucho más fácil, quiere decir que los pasos que le son característicos, son rastreros, y su compás precipitado y veloz, lo que no da lugar á que en el se puedan ejecutar pasos desplegados y majestuosos, como se pueden hacer en el bolero : á pesar de todo lo dicho, las mudanzas simples del bolero se combinan muy bien en el fandango: la regla que se debe de observar en él es la siguiente. Colocados que estén los bailarines uno en frente de otro como en el bolero, principiarán con el paseo, el cual no se debe hacer más que cuatro veces alternativamente una con cada pie, pues las repeticiones siempre son molestas; en seguida se hará una mudanza, después de la cual se vuelve a repetir el paseo al que le seguirá otra mudanza, y principiarán a pasar mudando el puesto, bien entendido que el hombre dará siempre el derecho a la muger : esta pasada se hace con ciertos pasos de burea abiertos, batiendo la planta del pie en tierra, doblando un poco las rodillas, teniendo el cuerpo bien derecho, y alzando ó bajando los brazos : el dicho paseo

se sigue siempre, hasta haber pasado y dado un giro, quedándose uno en frente de otro; desde cuya situación se rompe de nuevo con el paseo, haciéndolo dos veces intermediado de dos mudanzas, como antecederentemente hizo cada uno en su primitivo sitio, al cual vuelven de nuevo á pasar para ejecutar por tercera vez otros dos paseos con sus respectivas mudanzas, con una de las cuales se concluye. Ninguna provincia hay en España en que no se conozca el fandango; ya con el nombre de rondeñas, de malagueñas, &c. queriendo cada Reino ó provincia que se le deba la invención del referido baile; con efecto, es el mas característico de los bailes españoles; y el célebre don Tomás de Iriarte en su poema de la música, hablando del chiste y gracia que tiene el aire del fandango, dice así:

¿En qué bárbaro clima
al baile no se anima
con diversos tañidos
por costumbre heredados, no aprendidos?
dígalo solamente
el mas usual en la española gente,
que en dos compases únicos, ceñidos
á medida ternaria,
admitir suele exornación tan varia,
que en ella los primores
del gusto, ejecución y fantasía
apurán los mas diestros profesores:
el airoso fandango, ¡que alegría
infunde en nacionales y extrangeros
en los sabios y ancianos mas severos!
Canto 5, p. 113

An old Spanish dance, and that which has been conserved for longest in use in theater, the fandango, like most Spanish dance, is in triple-time, happy and lively: its duration is not precisely marked; and according to the caprice of whoever is dancing it may be longer or shorter. The fandango has much grace: it is not a dance of such capacity as the bolero, nor does it require so much art to dance, because although the bolero is in part an imitation of the fandango, all in all, [the fandango] is much easier, which means that its characteristic steps are dragged, and its rhythm precipitated and fast, which does not allow within it the execution of unfolded and majestic steps, as can be done in the bolero, despite all this, the simple mudanzas of the bolero work very well in the fandango: the rule that should be followed is the following. The dancers standing one in front of the other as in the bolero, will begin with the paseo, which should not be done more than four times alternating

Figure 3. Marcos Telléz Villar, Campanelas de las Seguidillas Boleras. c. 1790, estampa aguafuerte y buril. Courtesy of the Biblioteca Nacional de España.

between feet, because repetitions are always bothersome; right afterwards there will be a mudanza, after which is repeated the paseo followed by another mudanza, and the dancers begin to pass, changing places [pasar mudando el puesto]; it should be well understood that the man must always give his right to the woman: this pasada is done with certain open pas de bourees (pasos de burea abiertos), beating the sole of the foot on the ground (batiendo la planta del pie en tierra), bending the knees a little, and keeping the body very straight, and lifting or lowering the arms: the afore-mentioned paseo always follows (se sigue siempre) until having passed (pasado) and completed a revolution, finishing one in front of the other; from which place they begin again with the paseo, doing it twice, broken up by two mudanzas, as each did earlier in his previous place, to which they return with a pasada (vuelven de nuevo a pasar) to execute for the third time two more paseos with their respective mudanzas, with one of which the dance concludes. There is no province in Spain that does not know the fandango; maybe with the name of rondeñas, malagueñas, etc., each kingdom or province wishing to claim credit for the aforementioned dance; in effect, it is the most characteristic of Spanish dances, and the celebrated don Tomas de Iriarte in his poem about music, speaking of the humor and grace of the air of the fandango says thus...

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